

SIGNIFICANT ISSUES OF FORMING AND DEVELOPING WRITING SUBSKILLS

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Annotation: The article discovers importance of writing skill and basic procedures to improve writing. On the other hand, role of educational strategies to develop writing were analyzed. Moreover, basic strategies of developing writing comprehension and the system of exercises for developing writing were given.

Key words: *grammar structure, proficiency, inseparable aspects, essential skill, academic writing, acquire print, exam rubric.*

The developing of the language skills has always been a very hard and an interesting task. The process of writing suggests that we can actually teach students how to write with coherence, an appropriate grammar structure and an acceptable spelling. One of the effective ways to do this is to motivate the students and make them aware of the steps involved in effective writing. Four reasons why students dislike writing are:

1. It leaves as more permanent record of proficiency than speaking; so it seems a threat for them.
2. Students feel that they lack sufficient knowledge of the language.
3. Students believe that writing must be grammatically correct.
4. They think that formal correctness must be achieved at their very first attempt.

The seven effective writing strategies are: 1) Pre-writing; 2) early composing;

3) planning and organizing; 4) later composing; 5) final composing; 6) revising; 7) editing;

When we talk about writing is necessary to remember that there are three inseparable aspects when teaching it; Writing as a channel of a Foreign Language (FL) is the use of it alongside listening, speaking and reading in the process of learning important elements of the language. In our times, there is an increasing tendency of showing communication rather than the mere practice of linguistic forms. But we have to be careful because texts are made of sentences putting together for communicative purposes[1]. That is, you can not make bricks without straw and you can not build houses without bricks. So, to begin writing it is important to know the function of it, for instance, Advising, Reporting, etc.

The writing activities should be geared to their needs and interests. They should be linked to the real life whenever possible. In our present work we pretend to give useful information about the developing of writing skills and give some practical teaching ideas for this purpose contributing to improve teacher's knowledge about this topic. Then, we would like to state what the word practical means. According to Webster's Dictionary it means:

- capable of being put to use,
- useful thing,
- disposed to action,
- opposed to speculation or abstraction,
- qualified by practice or practical training by experience and also concerned with ethical decisions.

From our point of view, a practical teaching idea has something to do with a good idea, characterized by being attractive, exciting, aplicable to real life and taking into account the enviroment, context and most of all, the learners' needs and interests. Thus, teachers should know how to teach writing to be effective. Basically, writing is one of the fundamental skills that our students need to

develop[2]. Aside from the fact, that writing is an essential skill needed in communication, it is basically needed for our learners to succeed in their academic and personal lives. Teaching our students to become effective writers is part of our challenges as teachers. It demands not only our best strategies and practices but also our patience and determination. Also, it is a skill that is mastered through continued practice and drills.

Mastering writing skills is important due to its need in almost all the professions which need documentation, especially in this era. It is necessary to enter any modern workplace with good writing skills. According to Zhu (2004), business world requires and expect potential employers with good writing skills and they are seen as the clients of corporate world. Therefore, it is vital to equip oneself with good writing skills to get appointed and to disclosed to more job opportunities. In other words, employee with good writing skills are seen as “hot commodities” Other than that, it is one of the most serious skill to the acquired in tertiary education. Academic writing in tertiary is not just words but meaningful communication. Zhu (2004) added that academic writing includes understanding of distinctive procedures of ideas and interaction which needs basic or general writing abilities as a foundation[3]. Besides that, writing promotes creativity, imagination, and understanding. Writing is a thinking process which involves brain process, in order to organise ideas to write, writers need to imagine and be creative in putting their thoughts in words.

In methodological point it should be noted that At the beginning level (2-4 classes) we teach graphics in EL (handwriting), i.e. teaching to write letters (alphabet) which interrelates with teaching reading as graphic-phonemic correspondence. Pupils must acquire print hand letters. At the same time we form elementary writing skills for conducting communicative-cognitive objectives in the written form. On the material of sentences and not complicated texts pupils must write: a) holiday and birthday congratulations in cards; b) personal data: name and

surname, dates, address; c) short messages and personal letters; d) a plan, questions to short texts; e) description of pictures. The second stage (5-9 classes) at school must provide more intensive development of writing skills in different situations of communication. Topics and capacity of writing messages is broaden; the quality of produced text in the written form is improved. As a productive language skill, writing is much more than simply putting words on paper. A complex set of linguistic and cognitive processing skills come into play every time someone composes a message for a reader. Like speaking, writing almost always happens as part of a communicative event, with the written message designed for a specific reader (even when the reader is the same person as the writer).

When planning to teach a writing-focused lesson, whatever the genre or topic your students will write to, it is essential that writing is seen as a communicative act, not simply a solo activity to be graded by the teacher. There are several ways of ensuring this level of engagement with writing, starting with the way you frame writing tasks in class. Every writer needs a reader, so this should be a consideration in every learner's mind from early in a writing lesson[4]. Take some time to think who the reader will be and what they are expecting from the piece that they will read. Exam essay writing, for example, will be read by an assessor looking for certain features outlined in the task or exam rubric. A typical 'letter to a friend' needs to appeal personally to someone known to the writer, and even the notes that a learner takes in class should be useful to the reader (the student him/herself) when they come back to look at them later in their study. When planning writing tasks, leave time in the lesson for the writers to become critical readers of each others' work, posing as the intended reader from the writing event. Role-play being an examiner, and give the students sets of criteria to mark from, or ask them to get into the character of a teacher, newspaper reader, grandmother or whoever is specified as the reader in the writing task. Only by taking on this role and experiencing each others' writing in the relevant context can

the true effectiveness and feeling of a piece of writing be judged. Another good way to extend writing activity and increase written communication is to have students write responses to each others' pieces. Writing a letter or email to a friend can easily lead to the friend writing a reply, picking up points from the original piece and continuing the communication accordingly. This doubles the opportunity for written practice in the chosen genre, and increases interaction through the written word.

To sum up all given facts above, it should be noted that ESL teachers are is best to employ Process based approach, especially in teaching of secondary level and tertiary level education. Undoubtedly true, adult students are more independent and they possess sufficient knowledge in content and their language mastery is greater than the younger ESL learner as they are novice writers. Due, to these advantages possessed by adult learners, it will be undemanding for these learners to employ the writing process systematically. Finding supports these ideas, as most of the studies selected process-based approach studies which are done towards university participants. Thus, to scaffold the teaching of writing in higher education level, process writing will be the best approach. Meanwhile, in secondary and primary school level, process-product approach and process-genre approach will be suitable to be employed in the ESL classrooms, as scaffolding is given importance when selecting these approaches. Younger students need scaffolding in order to produce a good writing.

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